

Novel biomarkers in phenotypes of post-cardiac arrest syndrome and following presumed cause of death: Study design of a retrospective cohort study

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Introduction

The mortality of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) is high, and less than half of patients admitted to intensive care after sustained return of spontaneous circulation survive to hospital discharge.¹ The complex pathophysiological changes after cardiac arrest leading to death can be summarized as post-cardiac arrest syndrome (PCAS).^{2,3} Key components of PCAS include hypoxic-ischaemic brain injury, arrest-related myocardial dysfunction, systemic ischaemic-reperfusion response and persistent precipitating pathology.² Arrest-related myocardial dysfunction, and multiorgan failure following systemic ischaemic-reperfusion response are the most common causes of death in the first days after cardiac arrest. Thereafter, withdrawal of life-sustaining treatment (WLST) due to poor prognosis for neurological recovery based on severe hypoxic-ischaemic brain injury is the most common cause of death.²

In recent years, assays for novel biomarkers in blood have been developed for use on fully automated, random-access instruments with short turn-around time which could become suitable as routine clinical tests.

We here present the protocol for an exploratory study on potential blood biomarkers for PCAS, which could be used to early identify patients who might benefit from targeted interventions. We previously demonstrated that Neurofilament light (NFL) is the most promising blood biomarker of brain injury to date for prediction of neurological outcome after cardiac arrest.⁴ Cardiac biomarkers include N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP), commonly used in diagnosing heart failure and high-sensitivity troponin T (hs-TnT), used as a marker for acute coronary syndrome.^{5,6} Growth differentiation factor-15 (GDF-15) is a cytokine associated to inflammation and released from acute and chronic cellular stressors in large variety of cell types.⁷ Soluble Fms-like tyrosine kinase-1 (sFlt-1), also known as soluble vascular endothelial growth factor receptor-1 (sVEGFR-1), is an antiangiogenic factor associated with endothelial dysfunction and proposed as a marker for septic shock.⁸ As PCAS shares similarities with sepsis and that endothelial injury is associated with the severity of PCAS, make sFlt-1 a candidate biomarker to explore.^{2,9}

The aim of this study is to describe phenotypes of PCAS based on presumed cause of death using novel biomarkers representing cardiovascular, endothelial, inflammatory and neurological injury. Another aim of the study is to investigate the ability of biomarkers to discriminate death at 30 days.

Methods

Study Design

This is a biomarker study nested within the prospective, international Targeted Hypothermia versus Targeted Normothermia after Out-of-Hospital Cardiac Arrest (TTM2) trial. Adult unconscious patients (≥ 18 years) admitted to the intensive care unit after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest with presumed cardiac or unknown cause of arrest were randomized to either targeted hypothermia (33°C) or targeted normothermia ($\leq 37.8^{\circ}\text{C}$) between November 2017 and January 2020.^{10, 11} 24 of 61 sites participated in the biomarker study. This study was approved by the Regional Ethics Board in Lund, Sweden (Dnr 2015/228, 2017/36, 2017/662). Ethics committees in each participating country approved the protocol and decided whether initial written informed consent was waived, deferred, or obtained from a legal representative. In addition, informed consent was later obtained from each patient who regained mental capacity.¹¹

Sample collection and biochemical analysis

Serum samples were prospectively collected as part of the biobank substudy in the TTM2 trial at 0, 24, 48 and 72 hours after admission to intensive care as previously described.¹² Serum samples of NFL, NT-proBNP, hs-TnT, GDF-15 and sFlt-1 were analyzed with Elecsys immunoassays by Roche Diagnostics International AG in Penzberg, Germany.

Neurological prognostication and withdrawal of treatment

Prognostication for neurological outcome was performed at the earliest at 96 hours after inclusion, after which decisions on withdrawal of life-support (WLST) could be made, as previously described.¹¹ Data regarding presumed cause of death classified as cardiac, neurological, multiorgan failure or other cause (for instance, death due to comorbidities) was registered by treating physician during the trial.

Outcomes

Primary outcome will be the presumed cause of death as estimated by the treating physician. Secondary outcome will be all-cause mortality at 30 days after cardiac arrest.

Statistical analysis

We will describe patient characteristics of included and excluded patients. Any patient with a documented presumed cause of death, and available samples of all five investigated biomarkers at least one timepoint (0, 24, 48 or 72 hours after admission to ICU) will be included. We hypothesized that the 24-hour time point will be most informative, but for completeness, we will present results from all timepoints.

Biomarkers will be normalized using appropriate methods. Latent profile analysis (LPA) will be used to identify biomarker profiles. Associations of identified biomarker profiles with presumed

cause of death will be investigated, as well as differences of biomarker profiles at multiple timepoints.

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves will be produced from logistic regression models to assess ability of biomarkers to discriminate death at 30 days. Descriptive statistics will be presented with median and interquartile range (IQR) or frequency and percentage. Statistical analyses will be performed using R. Two-tailed $p \leq 0.05$ will be considered statistically significant and 95% confidence intervals will be reported when appropriate.

Discussion

The complex pathophysiological changes constituting PCAS represent potential therapeutical targets for patients' treatment with intensive care after cardiac arrest. Identification of potential markers representing the different phenotypes of this syndrome may increase physicians' ability to personalize care and accurately predict patient outcomes. In this study, we plan to examine the ability of a panel of serum biomarkers to differentiate phenotypes of PCAS and investigate how well the phenotypes are aligned with presumed cause of death.

To find these phenotypes, we will use latent profile analysis (LPA). LPA is a method to identify hidden groups from observed continuous variables. This method assumes there is a latent categorical variable dividing the population into different groups.^{13, 14} LPA is person-centered as it gives each individual in a cohort a probability value for inclusion in each group.¹⁴

Strengths of the study are the international multicentre design with prospectively collected blood samples within the first four days post-arrest. The standardized approach to intensive care treatment, neurological prognostication, withdrawal of life-sustaining therapy and follow-up are further strengths of the TTM2 trial. Limitations which could affect conclusions of the current biomarker study are the deaths of some patients between sampling timepoints, resulting in varying cohorts from day to day. Neurological prognostication was postponed until 96 hours after cardiac arrest with the aim of decreasing the risk of self-fulfilling prophecies from treatment withdrawal.^{10, 11}

The majority of patients included in the TTM2 trial had a presumed cardiac cause of arrest, and our results may not be generalizable to patients with other causes of arrest, or with an arrest occurring in hospital.

Conclusion

This exploratory biomarker study has the potential to provide new insights in the complex PCAS by describing profiles of novel serum biomarkers in relation to presumed cause of death.

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